

Effects of training and development on the performance of employees of non-governmental organizations in the northern region of Ghana

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(02), 531–538

Publication history: Received on 28 September 2022; revised on 08 November 2022; accepted on 11 November 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.2.1149>

Abstract

The quality of an organization's human resources is indispensable to its success. This insight has inspired many organizations to focus on enhancing the quality of their employees in order to increase productivity and efficiency. Training and development is one way for accomplishing this. The significance of training and development can only be appreciated if the direct impact on employee performance is understood. The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of training and development on the performance of employees of Non-Governmental Organisations in the Northern region of Ghana and to produce verifiable evidence of the impact of employee training on performance. The study comprised a sample size of 150 respondents who were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Data collection was done through closed-ended questionnaire administered to the respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and the results were presented in tables. The study results found a significant relationship between training and development and employee performance, and that off-the-job training and development programs have mainly contributed to increasing performance and productivity of employees of Non-Governmental Organizations in the Northern region of Ghana. Furthermore, the study discovered that on-the-job training has little to no effect on employee performance. The study recommends that the leadership of Non-Governmental Organizations in Northern Ghana should establish off-the-job training models for their employees if they want to increase productivity and efficiency.

Keywords: Training and Development; On-the-job training; Off-the-job training; Employee performance; Non-Governmental Organisations; Organisation Development

1. Introduction

Organizations of all kinds must adapt to both internal and external changes in order to survive in a continuously changing world [1]. As a result, many organizations are implementing a wide range of policies that will allow them to stay abreast of current events and practices. To combat the industry's volatility throughout the past few decades, many organizations have turned to staff training and development as a major tactic. It has been suggested that in order for an organization to stay competitive, employees must continuously upgrade their skills and competencies to enhance their job performance, growth, and ability to adapt to fast-changing economic situations [2].

Training and development refer to the methodical acquisition of knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that individuals need in order to perform satisfactorily on a certain activity or job [3]. The procedure improves an organization's capacity to transform its workforce through planned and unexpected learning. The improvement of job satisfaction among employees, as well as dedication, motivation, and group empowerment, can all be attained through training [4]. The application of contemporary techniques and fresh learning theories is a significant factor in training. Utilizing

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effective training techniques that may grab employees' attention and accelerate learning is essential for effective training [5]. According to Heathfield [6], when employees receive the proper training and development at the appropriate time, the organization benefits greatly and performance improves. Employer-provided training and development, according to Black and Lynch [7], increases performance measures by almost 16%. Once more, according to Black and Lynch [7], returns on investments in training and development enhance performance by 20%.

Despite the fact that more research is being conducted into how training and development affect employee performance, there have been few such studies conducted in the field of non-governmental organizations (NGOs). For instance, earlier studies mainly concentrated on the banking sector [8]; public sector [9]; pharmaceutical [10] manufacturing [11], and other industries [12]. Additionally, a small number of studies in Ghana have also examined worker performance in industries like banking [13, 14], insurance [15], communication [16], and mining [17]. There don't seem to be many studies on how training and development affect NGOs' success in Ghana. Additionally, studies on training and development, such as those by Gunu et al. [17] and Adeniyi and Kola [18], indicated a positive correlation between training and development and employee and organizational performance. Agyei [14], and Sarpong-Nyavor [19], on the other side, discovered that there is no connection between training and development and organizational performance. The conclusions of the aforementioned research did not agree, necessitating more inquiry. It is also necessary to confirm whether comparable consequences would be duplicated in other industries. Based on the deficiencies identified above, the study is being done to assess the impact of training and development on the performance of employees, using NGOs in the Northern region of Ghana as a case.

2. Theoretical and conceptual frameworks

2.1. Training and development

According to Armstrong [20], training is "the formal and systematic alteration of behavior through learning that occurs as a result of education, instruction, development, and planned experience." It increases employees' aptitudes, competencies, and capacities for carrying out particular tasks inside the organization. On the other hand, development entails acquiring the knowledge, abilities, and other behaviors relevant to or required for a task or activity. It consists of things like experiences, formal educational commitments, and coaching [20]. A more thorough definition of training and development is provided by Investors in People (IIP) UK [21], who claim that it includes both formal and informal training and includes any action that enhances skills, knowledge, and behavior. Through training and development, businesses have been able to adapt to changing consumer tastes and preferences, lower employee attrition, hasten the learning curve for new hires, lower expenses, and increase employee loyalty [20]. According to Desmone, Werner, and Harris [22], the training and development process consists of four stages or steps. These are as follows:

2.1.1. Training Needs Assessment

This procedure determines whether or not training is necessary or required. Employee (personal), organizational, and task (job) analyses are the three types of analyses carried out. Training needs assessments frequently involve the use of techniques like observation, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, and document reviews.

2.1.2. Designing the Training and Development

When designing a training and development program, it is important to clearly define the goals, parameters, delivery channels, and methodologies that will be used. The goal of the training program is formed from the study of the training needs, which includes what needs to be done and accomplished. The management, supervisors, and employees of the organization frequently participate in the design of the organization's training and development programs.

2.1.3. Training and development implementation.

This has to do with executing the training program itself. The organization will confirm that the instructors have arrived and are prepared to instruct and learn, respectively.

2.1.4. Monitoring, Evaluation of Training and Development

At this stage, data are collected and analyzed to determine whether the training program is effective in achieving the goals set forth, and suggestions for improvement or change are made.

2.2. Classification of Training and Development

2.2.1. On-the-Job Training and Development (Informal Training)

In order to help employees develop a certain skill, some organisational managers prefer to organize on-the-job training and development [23]. One of the most significant benefits of on-the-job training and development is that organisations do not require additional facilities to train and develop their workforce. On-the-job training may be a continuous procedure that barely affects regular business operations. The organization trains its staff members using three standard methodologies. These are as follows:

Job Rotation

This method can be described as the procedure by which the trainee learns various jobs or functions at various points in an organization. In other words, the trainee switches between tasks in accordance with the predetermined timetable or schedule [24]. As a result of job rotation, the trainee can develop many skills. Because the learner learns a little bit about each work after training, they become generalists, which boosts job satisfaction and productivity.

Orientation/Induction

It addresses a scenario in which new hires receive training to help them become familiar with their jobs and the organization as a whole in terms of values, guidelines, and regulations [25]. Employee morale is raised by this technique, encouraging them to perform without making serious mistakes.

Apprenticeship

In this approach, an unskilled individual is trained by a skilled one. According to Noe [26], an apprenticeship combines classroom instruction with on-the-job training so that one can work and study at the same time (off-the-job). The trainee often works for and alongside the trainer, who is typically a senior professional and can take some time. Its key advantages are the ability to earn money while learning and the high likelihood of finding employment once the training is complete.

2.2.2. Off-the-Job Training (Formal Training)

According to Olaniyan and Ojo [25], off-the-job training may concentrate on the classroom with training seminars, lectures, and films although in some circumstances efforts are made to stimulate actual working conditions. An employee may participate in vestibule training in a different room than the one in which he would be working, using genuine tools and materials in a realistic work environment. This is done to alleviate workplace stress, which can impede learning. In addition to traditional classroom instruction, formal training may also take the form of day releases, in which staff members are given one or two days off each week or month to attend formal lectures [17]. The method also allows for the employment of a wider range of training techniques, such as lecturing, internships, and practicum, special studies, films, television, conferences or discussions, case studies, role acting, modeling, programmed teaching, and laboratory training.

Simulation/Vestibule

According to Htun [27], simulation refers to training employees in any isolated setting that is similar to the actual work situation, whereas vestibule refers to training employees using the prototype or the same equipment that is used in the workplace, but the training is conducted outside the workplace. Vestibules are typically utilized for educating semi-skilled staff as well as instructing multiple persons at once when equipment is unavailable. The main benefit of simulation is that it reduces the likelihood of training accidents, saving the organization money. It also reduces the level of dissatisfaction of the trainer because he is not functioning in an abstract setting. Furthermore, simulation allows employees to gain attitudes, concepts, knowledge, rules, or skills that will improve the trainee's performance.

Case Study

A case study is a problem-solving technique in which trainees are given practical or theoretical problems to evaluate, synthesize, solve, or ask questions about [28]. Organizations use case studies to help trainees improve their analytical, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills. It is also employed when active participation is required and the learning process includes questions and interpretations.

Role Play

This method has the learner act out and acquire the conduct and attitudes of another person as if he were the actual thing [29]. This strategy allows trainees to respect and comprehend people while also advising them. Managers utilize it to deal with difficulties such as conflict, absenteeism, and performance review.

Classroom/Lecture

A trainer uses this method to teach or convey information or concepts to trainees orally, with little or no participation from the trainees. The data could have come from his own reading, study, and experiences. According to Ahammad [30], this strategy is employed when a large number of people are being taught a large amount of material or when the training topic is extensive. Other training approaches, such as case studies and role acting, might be used to supplement this method.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

The model of the study was drawn from the literature review on training and development process.

Source: Authors' Construct, 2021.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

3. Methodology

3.1. Study design

The research method used in the study was descriptive-explanatory, allowing for in-depth description and analysis of the variables under inquiry, characterizing and describing their properties, and evaluating and describing their relationships without manipulation. Additionally, the design allowed for the creation of generalizations using both inductive and deductive reasoning.

3.2. Research population and sample

The study employed simple random sampling technique to select 150 respondents from 32 NGOs in the northern region of Ghana. The respondents were a mix of upper- and lower-level employees in the NGO sector.

3.3. Data Collection

The data for this study was gathered via a structured survey comprising 26 items. All questions are closed-ended with the use of the five-point Likert scale consisting of strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree. Ten questionnaires were distributed to pilot project participants in order to assess the instruments' validity and reliability. Six of them returned. The results assisted the researchers in improving the structure and content of the questionnaire. The surveys were collected from the respondents over the course of a week. A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed, with 150 of them returned.

3.4. Statistical analysis method

The researchers analyzed data using quantitative research methodology. The analysis of the questionnaire was undertaken using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 21). Following the collection of survey data, a number of steps are required to analyze the data and provide valuable information. Making certain that the statistics are correct is an element of this. The validity of the pre-test data was assessed using Cronbach Alpha. According to the Cronbach Alpha reliability study, the closer the Alpha is to 1.0, the more consistently trustworthy the internal consistency is. Other statistical tools such descriptive statistics, and regression among others were used in analysing the data.

4. Results

4.1. Reliability statistics

Table 1 Cronbach alpha reliability results

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.893	26

Source: SPSS 21

According to Table 1, the Cronbach's alpha on the test of measurement reliability for all variables was 0.893, which exceeded the usually recognized criterion of 0.70. As a result, the measurement is reliable.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistical analysis is used to demonstrate the construct's validity. This is generally done via standard deviation and descriptive means. While mean deviation is a measure of how much individual data deviate from the mean, standard deviation is a more accurate and detailed measure of dispersion.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	N	mean	std. deviation
On-the-job training	150	2.0067	0.37068
Off-the-job training	150	1.9773	0.40353

Source: SPSS 21

The result in table 2 shows that on-the-job training had the highest mean, with a mean score of 2.0067, and a standard deviation of 0.37068, which suggest that the respondents agree highly with the fact that employee in the NGO sector in the northern region of Ghana learn more about their job or the latest advancements in their field whiles they are engaged in productive work on-the-job. The results also shows that off-the-job training had the lowest mean score of 1.9773, and a standard deviation of 0.44272, which is an indication that the respondents agree that the training needs of the employees take place whiles at a location away from their workplace. When employers hold training away from the workplace, it helps minimize distractions so employees can fully focus on the material they're learning.

4.3. Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is used in the research study to examine how independent variables affect dependent variables. The following is the multiple regression model:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where

Y is Performance of Lecturers (dependent variable)

α is constant

X is another factor affecting Performance

β is the regression coefficient that may positively or negatively affect dependent and independent variables.

$$\text{Employee Performance (Dependent Variable)} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{ on-the-job training} + \beta_2 \text{ off-the-job training} + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Table 3 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.229	2	12.115	357.927	0.000 ^b
	Residual	4.975	147	0.034		
	Total	29.204	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance; b. Predictors: (Constant), Off-the-job training, On-the-job training

In table 3, the F value is 357.927 and it is less than $P \leq 0.05$. This suggests that the overall regression model is valid, fit, and statistically significant. A valid regression model implies that all independent variables are contributing to the existence of a significant and positive relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable.

Table 4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.911 ^a	0.830	0.827	0.18397	0.830	357.927	2	147	0.000

Predictors: (Constant), off-the-job training, On-the-job training.

Table 4 shows a regression coefficient 'R' of 0.911 or 91.1%, indicating that there is a relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination 'R²' is 0.830, indicating that off-the-job and on-the-job training and development explain 83.0% of the variation in the performance of employees in the NGO sector in Ghana's northern region.

4.4. Correlation Coefficient

Table 5 The correlation coefficient for the variables under consideration

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-0.129	0.084		-1.527	0.129
	On-job-training	0.968	0.141	0.810	6.858	0.000
	Off-job-training	0.115	0.130	0.104	0.884	0.378

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance; Source: SPSS 21

5. Discussions

The purpose of this research was to investigate the impact of training and development on the performance of NGOs in the Northern region of Ghana. The tables show the results of linear regression on data collected from 150 respondents via questionnaires. According to the criterion, if the p-value is less than 0.05, it is significant. According to the results in table 5, on-the-job training and development have a regression co-efficient (β) of 0.810, which means that if all other factors are held constant, every 1% increase in employee on-the-job training and development in Ghana boosts employee performance by 81.0%. The T-value is 6.858 and significant at the 0.000 level, which is less than the P-value of 0.05. There is thus sufficient evidence to suggest that on-the-job training has little to no impact on employee performance in the NGO sector. Again, the regression coefficient (β) for off-the-job training and development of employees is 0.104, implying that, if all other factors remain constant, every 1% increase in off-the-job training and development of employees in the NGO sector leads to a 10.4% increase in employee performance. The T value is 0.884, and the level of statistical significance is 0.378, which is greater than the P-value of 0.05. It suggests that off-the-job training has a major impact on employee performance. This conclusion contradicts the findings of Ndayisba [31], and Worlu, Mugri, and Akpakip [32], who discovered a substantial link between on-the-job training and employee performance. However, the findings are similar to previous findings by Sarpong-Nyavor [19], Tarus [33], and Rashki, Hasanqasemi, and Mazidi [34], who discovered that off-the-job training has a significant impact on employee

performance. This study's findings add to the existing literature by suggesting that on-the-job and off-the-job training has an effect on the performance of employees in the NGO sector. One major limitation of this study was that it was restricted to NGOs in the Northern region rather than the entire country. The results could have been impacted by socioeconomic and environmental factors.

6. Conclusion

Human resource management now plays a bigger part in running an organisation and improving employee performance. An important component of human resources is training and development. For improved performance, it is crucial for organisations to hire qualified, skilled workers. Staff members are more competent when they possess the necessary knowledge and abilities. Employees would have possibilities through training and development to improve their career prospects and status within the organization. Organizational effectiveness would improve as a result. Nevertheless, if personnel are trained and skilled, they will outperform others who are untrained and unskilled as resources and assets for the organization. One method for optimizing employee performance and boosting organizational productivity and growth is to determine what training model works best in the NGO sector. Although there is a ton of study on training and development, most of it has not been done among NGOs in northern Ghana. This study adds to the sparse but growing body of knowledge on training and development in Ghana and throughout Africa. The study's conclusions showed that employees of NGOs in the northern region of Ghana supported off-the-job training and believed it to be a major contributor to productivity and performance. This study showed that NGOs in Northern Ghana's leadership had no choice but to implement off-the-job training and development if they are interested in increasing productivity and efficiency.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank all the employees of the NGOs who spent valuable time to respond to the questionnaires of this study.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors agree that there is no conflict of interest.

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